

STUDY OF THE POSSIBILITIES OF USING ADSORBENTS OBTAINED FROM WOOD PROCESSING WASTES IN THE CLEANING OF OIL-CONTAMINATED OBJECTS

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Abstract

The article examines the possibilities of using adsorbents, especially adsorbents made based on wood processing waste, for cleaning oil pollution from various objects. The purpose of the article is to show the advantage of wood processing waste, which is a natural raw material that is inexpensive, renewable, and does not cause toxicity to the environment during the application of adsorbents in oil pollution.

Keywords: petrol, adsorbent, sawdust, bark, sawdust.

Introduction

Spillage of crude oil on land and in seas has caused interest in developing environmentally friendly and efficient methods for cleaning up these pollutions, because of the toxic and dangerous effects of a number of hydrocarbon components in the marine environment, ecology and humans. Crude oil spilled on land or in the marine environment immediately undergoes physical, chemical and biological changes. Crude oil, which is usually lighter than water in the sea, will spread to the surface of the water. Later, an oil layer about 1 mm thick forms on the surface of the water. The rate at which oil spreads on a water surface depends on the type of oil, water temperature and weathering processes, for example; atmospheric temperature, wind speed. The lighter components of oil tend to evaporate into the atmosphere. The degree of evaporation and its rate of occurrence depend on the volatility of oil [1].

Cleaning of petroleum products in wastewater is a serious problem for many enterprises of various industries (oil refining, oil, machine building, energy). Nowadays, there are many methods of cleaning oil-contaminated objects using various reagents and adsorbents, most of them are economically inefficient, expensive and not always effective. Therefore, finding cheap and effective adsorbents for cleaning objects contaminated with oil is an important and urgent task [2].

A number of studies have been conducted on natural fibrous materials used as adsorbents, with special attention paid to cases where bark, sawdust, straw, grain hulls, flax processing waste, and peat are used for this purpose. Cellulose is of special importance as one of the important structural components of plant materials. Biomass, derived from plants or animals and mostly in the form of agricultural waste, refers to organic adsorbents as carbon-based material. Globally, 5 billion tons of agricultural biomass waste are produced annually, equivalent to approximately 1.2

billion tons of oil heat equivalent, or 25% of current world production. Adsorbents based on woodworking waste are based on renewable resources, are non-toxic, non-corrosive, fully active during recycling, and inexpensive. Wood processing waste resources are irreplaceable materials such as agricultural waste that contribute to the prevention of global warming, but also have high potential for use in oil spill cleanup in terms of ensuring full sustainability and reproducibility. Oil holding capacity of adsorbents, buoyancy, water solubility of hydrocarbons are used to compare sorption capacities for adsorbents [1].

Due to the continuous increase of anthropogenic load on the environment, the problem of water pollution is currently more urgent. Environmental problems are more pronounced in regions where chemical production is carried out. The leading positions in the list of priority pollutants are oil and oil products (petroleum), heavy metals, organic and inorganic synthetic products contained in wastewater from dyeing and many other industries. Oily waste water is divided into two different groups: the first - as a result of accidents and unauthorized discharge of oil products, as well as from urban and industrial facilities, ports, etc. are natural reservoirs polluted by surface water; the second - extraction, storage, processing and transportation of crude oil, washing of any type of transport, etc. waste water (TS) generated as a result of technological processes in facilities. The treatment process for oil pollution of waste water requires that it can be reused or discharged into natural water bodies. Cleaning the surface of water bodies from contamination involves removing the oil layer by mechanical, physical-chemical biological methods. The most promising and ecologically feasible method is the removal of the oil layer with the help of oil sorbents. Extracted oil can be free and dissolved. As a result of sedimentation, oil is extracted. Conventionally, flotation cleaning methods and

electrocoagulation are used to remove finely dispersed and associated oil. There are many methods of preparation of sorbents and filter materials for net water purification and their application schemes [3].

Although there are existing technologies to eliminate the effects of oil pollution using various sorbent materials, both natural and synthetic, natural adsorbents are more ecologically safe. Conventional sorbents cause great difficulties in their application. During the collection of oil and oil products, oil-absorbing sorbents form multi-kilogram oil conglomerates that are difficult to collect from the surface of water or soil. In addition, the negative effect comes from the sorbents themselves, as the adsorbents themselves bring additional pollution to the environment. A promising direction is the development of technologies that use bioactive adsorbents in the purification of oil and oil products in various environments, including breaking down oil products through biodegradation [4].

In particular, oil spill cleanup sorbents must meet stringent requirements to be most effective in oil removal, to absorb oil rather than water, and to be able to quickly saturate with oil. Moreover, it must be able to stay afloat and maintain buoyancy even when saturated with oil. When selecting sorbents for spill cleanup, the existing oil yield capacity of the sorbent and the method of disposal of the oiled sorbent material should also be considered. Among the natural fibrous materials used as sorbents, special attention should be paid to straw, grain hulls, flax processing waste, sawdust and peat. Cellulose is particularly important as one of the important structural components of plant materials[5].

The possibility of using an adsorbent in the conditions of drilling platforms is determined, first of all, by its physico-mechanical, physico-chemical properties, for example, wear resistance, hardness, mass density, storage capacity, water adsorption, oil product adsorption, full saturation capacity. The characteristics of parameters specific to adsorbents are determined as a result of their complex laboratory studies. For this, heating was conducted in a muffle furnace in a temperature range of 200-450°C with a step of 50°C for 45 minutes. Then, the retention capacity and adsorption of petroleum products were determined for each sample. The dynamic sorption capacity was determined by modeling the oil-contaminated wastewater treatment process at temperatures of 350°C, 400°C and 450°C for the original and modified sorbent. The oil-contaminated water sample was passed through the adsorbent layer in the sorption column. The concentration of oil products in the adsorbent and purified water was determined by the fluorometric method [6].

The production and consumption of porous materials has a steady growth trend. In particular, the global consumption of porous carbon materials (PCM) is about 1.1 million tons per year and continues to grow at 9% per year. At the same time, the main amount of activated carbon (80-85%) is produced from non-renewable sources. A wide range of PCM can be obtained on the basis of large tonnage wastes of

chemical and mechanical processing of wood: sawdust, bark, logging waste and industrial lignins [7].

As researchers continue to synthesize adsorbents using agricultural wastes, the use of agro-based materials as adsorbents has received wide recommendations. Some of these agro-based materials include, but are not limited to, peanut shells, sawdust, coconut shells, and banana peels. As a follow-up, researchers attempted to synthesize an alternative adsorbent for the remediation of crude oil-contaminated water using coconut shell by activation method. On the other hand, it is possible to present agricultural wastes as good adsorbents because they are available at no cost [8].

Among various agricultural wastes, the synthesis of activated carbon (AC) from bamboo and banana fibers also has a unique place because of its high sorption capacity as one of the most promising methodologies or applications in oil spill cleanup. The physicochemical properties of synthesized AC samples were analyzed by FTIR spectra and N₂ physisorption. [9].

The possibilities of using modified wood processing wastes for removal of diesel engine oil from heavy oil products from the surface of water by sorption were also investigated. Sawdust of linden tree (*Tilia cordata*) was used as sorption material, and spent diesel engine oil was used as sorbate. In order to increase the sorption capacity of wood waste, it was affected by ultrasound at a frequency of 35000 Hz in an aqueous medium for 4 hours. The physical and mechanical properties of modified sawdust were determined: mass density, ash content, buoyancy. Experiments conducted on the modeling of engine oil spills on the surface of water showed that the use of ultrasonically treated linden sawdust is a more effective sorption material for diesel engine oils. Under static adsorption conditions, the degree of water purification has reached 99% [10].

The analysis of the reviewed literature shows that the most ecologically clean, inexpensive, renewable, non-polluting, accessible material for cleaning oil and oil products from various water and soil bodies is wood processing waste.

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REFINEMENT OF THE ALGORITHM OF WORK OF THE CODGRABBER INTERLOCK DEVICE

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ДОРАБОТКА АЛГОРИТМА РАБОТЫ УСТРОЙСТВА БЛОКИРОВКИ РАБОТЫ КОДГРАББЕРА

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Abstract

In this work the algorithm of work of anticodgrabber on the basis of ATtiny84 microcontroller, which constitutes bouncing dialogical code.

Аннотация

В работе рассмотрен алгоритм работы антикодграббера на базе микроконтроллера ATtiny84, который представляет прыгающий диалоговый код.

Keywords: radio interference, transmission, package, interception.

Ключевые слова: радиопомеха, передача, посылка, перехват.

Решается задача защиты информации в микроконтроллерах устройств блокировки работы кодграббера, причем под защитой понимается противодействие считыванию информации кодграббером при открытии или закрытии автомобиля с помощью в автосигнализации С развитием технологий преступники все чаще начали использовать в своей деятельности всевозможные электронные устройства, которые позволяют деактивировать охранный комплекс или иммобилайзер. Наиболее

распространенное устройство - кодграббер, которое предназначено для обмана автомобильной сигнализации и последующего угона автомобиля.

Суть алгоритма работы антикодграббера: «Ставится задача разработать алгоритм «прыгающего» диалогового кода. Суть метода сводится к тому, что по псевдослучайному закону будут меняться правила (протокол) передачи информации. Передаваемая команда будет передаваться по ча-